

Comparative Study of Efficacy, Safety with Compliance of Intravenous Iron Sucrose and Intravenous Ferric Carboxymaltose for Treatment of Iron Deficiency Anemia in Pregnant Women: in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Worldwide, anemia is the most prevalent treatable condition in pregnant women, and it raises the risk of both maternal and neonatal death. The purpose of this study is to compare intravenous ferric carboxymaltose with intravenous iron sucrose in terms of their effectiveness, safety, and compliance in treating iron deficiency anemia in pregnant patients.

Methods: This study, which involved 100 pregnant women, was randomized and prospectively conducted in the department of obstetrics and Gynecology at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital in Laheriasarai, Bihar, between June 2019 and May 2020. Ferric carboxymaltose was administered intravenously to 50 pregnant anemic individuals, while iron sucrose was administered intravenously to the remaining 50 patients. Prior to and three weeks following therapy, measurements of hemoglobin, packed cell volume, and blood indices were made. Both intravenous substances' safety and effectiveness were investigated.

Results: Pregnancy-related anemia was shown to be more common in the 20–24 age range and in multigravida women during the 22–28 week gestational age range. Three weeks following therapy, the mean hemoglobin difference was 2.34 g/dl for ferric carboxymaltose and 1.32 g/dl for iron sucrose. Compared to iron sucrose, the other metrics likewise increased significantly for ferric carboxymaltose.

Conclusion: When treating iron deficiency anemia in pregnancy, ferric carboxymaltose is a more effective and superior option with fewer adverse effects and the added benefit of a single dosage schedule.

Keywords: Ferric carboxymaltose, Iron sucrose, Intravenous, Hemoglobin, Peripheral smear.

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Introduction

Anaemia is one of the world's leading causes of disability and it is one of the most serious public health hazards. [1] Anaemia refers to a state wherein the level of haemoglobin in the blood is below the reference range appropriate for that particular age and sex. [2]

Nutritional anaemia being the most common variant worldwide can be described as a disease syndrome caused by malnutrition. [3] It is found more commonly among women of childbearing age, children and during pregnancy and lactation. Nearly two-thirds of pregnant and one-half of non-pregnant women from the developing countries are seen to be affected by some form of nutritional anaemia. [4] The developed countries though less affected, are not completely free of anaemia, and a

significant percentage of women of child-bearing age i.e. about 4-12% suffer from anemia. [5] Globally, nutritional anaemia affects nearly half of pregnant women, with iron deficiency being recognized as the most common nutritional deficiency among women of childbearing age, in both developed and developing countries. [1,6] It is one of the major contributing factors in maternal morbidity and mortality in third world countries and according to the WHO, it contributes to 20% of the total maternal deaths. [7]

In India, about 20-40% of maternal deaths are due to anaemia. It is estimated that one in every two women in our country suffers from some form of anaemia. [8] The prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy in India as per the National Family

Health Survey (NFHS)-3 findings is 55.3%, with a prevalence of 57.4% and 50.9% in rural and urban areas respectively. [9–11] The WHO proposes that

“anaemia deficiency should be considered to exist” when the haemoglobin is below the following levels. [12,13]

Table 1: Hb levels for anaemia

Age/sex	Hb-g/dl (venous blood)	MCHC (%)
Adult males	13	34%
Adult females (non-pregnant)	12	34%
Adult females (pregnant)	11	34%
Children, 6 months to 6 Years	11	34%
Children, 6 to 14 years	12	34%

The normal MCHC should be 34 irrespective of the age group, any value below being considered abnormal. [14,15]

Material and Methods

A hospital-based, randomized, comparative study was conducted on all antenatal women attending Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar were studied over 12 months from June 2019 to May 2020. Based on the previous study¹⁴ the proportion of iron sucrose and ferric carboxymaltose groups are 86% and 14%, using 5% level of significance, 80% power. The total sample size is 100 antenatal women, 50 in each group. Patients will be selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria.

All Antenatal women with iron deficiency anaemia with Hb 6-10gm and peripheral smear suggestive of iron deficiency anaemia, gestational age 16-35 weeks and age group between 18-35 years were included in this study. History of parenteral iron intolerance, Chronic Kidney disease, Haematological disorder, Vitamin B12 and folate deficiency, Deep vein thrombosis, thrombocytosis, having Thalassemia or sickle cell disease and

history of recent blood transfusion were excluded in this study. Randomisation was done by computer-generated random numbers assigning patients to both groups-iron sucrose and iron carboxymaltose group.

Ferric Carboxymaltose was given as per the total required dose in normal saline infusion as follows:

- IV drip infusion: Dilute in 0.9% sodium chloride / 500 to 1000mg: 250 ml NS - 15 min duration.
- Not exceeding the maximum dose of 1000 mg /day/ week.
- Iron sucrose was given in a dose of 200 mg intravenously in 100ml normal saline over a period of 15-20 min on alternate days until the required total dose was administered; to the maximum dose of 600 mg/week.

Ganzoni Formula:

Deficit = (Target hb {12gm/dl} - Hemoglobin of the patient) × 2.4 × Weight in kg (pre pregnancy) + 1000 (storage). They were followed up after three weeks, for haemoglobin estimation to note the rise in haemoglobin values.

Results

Table 2 : Distribution of patients according to the severity of anemia

Hb level	No. of cases	Percentage
Mild anemia	7	7.0%
Moderate anemia	93	93.0%
Total	100	100.0%

Table 2 is showing 93% of patients were belongs to moderate anaemia.

Table 3 : Correlation between age and severity of anemia

Age (years)	Moderate anemia	Mild anemia	No. of cases	Percentage
<20	3	-	3	3.0
20-24	52	7	59	59.0
25-29	26	1	27	27.0
30-34	11	-	11	11.0
Total	92	8	100	100.0

Table 3 is showing 59.0% of anemic patients were belongs to the age group of 2-24 years, in that 52.0% of cases were moderate anemia and 7.0% of were mild anemia.

Table 4: Correlation between socioeconomic status and severity of anemia

SES	Moderate anemia	Mild anemia	Total no cases	Percentage
Upper middle class	39	4	43	43.0%
Lower middle class	53	4	57	57.0%
Total	92	8	100	100.0%
Chi-Square Test & P-value	$\chi^2 = 0.175$		P = 0.932, NS	

Table 4 is showing 43.0% of anemic patients were belongs to upper middle class and 57.0% of patients were belongs to the lower middle class, so according to our study anemia patients were more common in the lower middle class.

Table 5: Correlation between gravidity and severity of anemia

Gravidity	Moderate anemia	Mild anemia	No of cases	Percentage
Primi	33	6	39	39.0%
Multi	59	2	61	61.0%
Total	92	8	100	100.0%
Chi-Square Test & P-value	$\chi^2 = 4.73$		P = 0.039, S	

Table 5 is showing that anemia was more common in multigravida patients that were 61.0% and 39.0% patients were primi gravida.

Table 6: Correlation between gestational age and severity of anemia

Gestational age in weeks	Moderate anemia	Mild anemia	No. of cases	Percentage
15-21	20	-	20	20.0
22-28	56	7	63	63.0
29-35	16	1	17	17.0
Total	92	8	100	100.0

Table 6 shows that 63.0% of anemic patients were in the gestational age group of 22-28 weeks because of hemodilution.

Study observed that, majority of the cases 93 (93.0%) were belongs to the moderate (7-9%) Hb% level and 7 (7.0%) were belongs to the mild Hb% level. There was no statistical significant difference of Hb% level between the groups FCM and Iron sucrose (P>0.05). Study reveals that, there was no statistical significant difference of adverse effects

between the groups of FCM and Iron Sucrose (P>0.05). Study reveals that, there was statistically very highly significant difference of mean Hb% level before and after the treatment in FCM and Iron sucrose groups respectively (P<0.001).

After the treatment the mean HB% level has significantly increased in both the groups, therefore the treatment was effective in both the groups (P<0.001). But FCM group showed more increase the Hb% level as compare to Iron sucrose group.

Table 7 : Distribution of cases according to Hb level

Hb% level	FCM		Iron sucrose		Total	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
Moderate 7-9	46	92.0%	47	94.0%	93	93.0%
Mild 9-10	4	8.0%	3	6.0%	7	7.0%
Total	50	100.0%	50	100.0%	100.0	100.0%
Mean \pm SD	8.28 \pm 1.16		8.26 \pm 1.13		8.27 \pm 1.14	
t-test value and p-value	t=0.023, p=0.96, NS					

Table 8 : Distribution of cases according to adverse effect

Adverse effect	FCM		Iron sucrose		Total	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
No adverse effect	48	96.0%	49	98.0%	97	94.0%
Rashes	1	2.0%	1	2.0%	2	4.0%
Vomiting	1	2.0%	0	0	1	2.0%
Total	50	100.0%	50	100.0%	100	100.0%
Chi-square & p-value	$\chi^2 = 0.343$, p=0.937, NS					

Table 9 : Comparison of mean Hb% level before treatment and after 3 weeks treatment and also comparison between the groups

Group	Before Treatment Mean±SD	After Treatment Mean±SD	Mean difference	Paired t-test, p-value and significance
FCM	8.28± 0.39	10.62± 0.66	2.34	t=31.97P=0.000, VHS
Iron Sucrose	8.26± 0.34	9.57± 0.46	1.32	t=24.77P=0.000, VHS
Mean difference	0.02	1.05	-	-
Paired t-test	t=0.69	t=9.155	-	-
p-value and significance	P=0.778NS	P=0.000VHS	-	-

Discussion

Nutritional anemia in pregnancy is a public health problem especially in developing countries and the commonest is iron deficiency anemia. Anemia in pregnancy is significantly associated with both fetal and maternal morbidity. Rapid improvement of Hb and iron stores in pregnancy will improve the general health status of the patient and decrease complications.

The patients in our study belonged to the age group of 18-35 years. The Majority of them were of the age group of 19-24 years in both study groups. The mean age was found to be slightly lesser in our study (24.8±4.4 and 24.5±3.1 years) when compared to other studies such as Christoph P et al. [12] (29 and 29.9 years) and Patel J et al., [13] (29.1±2.4 and 28.4±3.7 yrs). This might suggest early marriage and pregnancy in patients in our study. Other maternal data such as Obstetric Index and gestational age though showed slight variations in either group were not significant as in other studies. Mean body weight (48.6 kg and 49.7 kg) was also significantly lower in our study as compared to prior studies (73.1 and 69.3 kg) by Christoph et al., [12] which suggests that patients in our study were poorly nourished.

Baseline Hb in our study was 7.8±1.2 g/dl in group 1 and 8.7±0.9g/dl in group 2, thus group 2 had anaemia to a slightly lesser degree. However, this did not account for bias as the patients received iron infusion depending on the dose calculated based on their respective Hb levels. The baseline Hb in other studies were slightly higher 9.7±0.9 and 9.5±4.9 g/dl in Christoph P et al., and 8.7±3.1 and 8.9±2.3 g/dl in Patel J et al, [12,13] This again suggests that our study population had slightly higher grades of anaemia and required more vigorous management. Serum ferritin levels were however comparable to other studies (12.8±29.1 mcg/L Christoph P et al.,) in group 1, 11.2±7.9 mcg/L. Group 2 however owing to a lesser degree of anaemia had raised baseline serum ferritin levels (20.1±13.6 mcg/L versus 7±5.65 mcg/L in Christoph P et al.,). [12] Other iron parameters such as serum iron and TIBC were also significantly better in group 2 (57.4 mcg/dl and 357.1 mcg/dl respectively). The mean iron required in group 1 of the present study was significantly

higher than group 2 (978.1 versus 882.8 mg). Likewise, the total iron infused was also more in group 1 (966.7 versus 743.3mg). Christoph P et al. [12] also showed similar differences in iron infused (933 versus 402 mg). Thus, our study population had iron deficiency and thus anaemia of higher severity.

In regards to the type of anaemia histologically, the majority of our patients had microcytic, hypochromic blood picture in both groups (65%) suggesting that majority had severe grades of iron deficiency. The present comparative study investigated the efficacy and safety of FCM and iron sucrose in IDA of pregnancy. It was seen that both IV iron preparations were effective in treating IDA in pregnancy. FCM therapy efficiently increased Hb, at the end of 3 weeks following treatment.

The Hb rise with FCM was 1.5 0.1g/dl at 3 weeks. These results are in line with several other studies. A study by Christoph P et al., [12] on 206 pregnant women with IDA showed a Hb increase of 1.5±1.1g/dl at the end of 3 weeks. A similar study by Pels A et al., in the Netherlands showed Hb increase of 2.3 g% in 3 weeks. Patel J et al., [13] had Hb increase of 5.2 g/dl, 15 days post treatment whereas the ferritin levels improved by 9.2 mcg/L. Hb and ferritin values also improved after treatment with iron sucrose. Our study at the end of 3 weeks showed Hb increment of 0.7 -1.4 mg/dl. Christoph P et al. [12] showed similar rise in Hb of 1.1g/dl in 4 weeks, whereas Patel J et al., [13] an Indian study, showed a rise of 3.7g/dl in 15 days. The ferritin increase in this previous Indian study was 9.2 mcg/L. Thus, in terms of efficiency, both FCM and iron sucrose showed improved results in our study as compared to several previous studies.

However, our study aimed to also compare the efficacy of FCM therapy to iron sucrose. At the end of 3 weeks, FCM showed significantly increased Hb and ferritin as compared to iron sucrose, post treatment. Thus, our study shows, that FCM is well tolerated in pregnant women and has fewer numbers of side effects as compared to iron sucrose even when given as a large dose.

Conclusion

In conclusion, fast-acting iron supplementation (FCM) not only quickly corrects hemoglobin levels but also replenishes the body's iron stores without causing significant side effects. Therefore, when administered to expectant mothers in the latter half of their pregnancy, the risk of anemia is addressed during gestation and may potentially be avoided during the postpartum phase. In the end, we have a mother in good health and a child in good health, which is every woman's birth right. This would greatly improve the quality of life and lessen the burden of maternal illness and mortality on a nationwide scale. Hence, all the health care providers, hospital administration and the government should take measures to make FCM easily available and affordable to the women who are in actual need of it and make use of this boon to eradicate.

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